

THE ROLE OF CONSORTIA AND DIGITAL PERSERVATION

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Introduction

Library Consortia traced back from 1886 dwelt up to “Library Cooperation ” in library journal. In 1887 in his article “Cooperation Versus Competition in Library Journal “ R.B.Downs express his view on library cooperation his paper “One for All: a Historical Sketch of Library Cooperation. nether effect made by ALA in 1939 symposium organized on library of Tomorrow they focused and impact of internet technology and inter landing cooperation issues and resources sharing they indentified and need of user need to satisfied y the browning material one place to another library which were not available with individual library. In this junction academic library have formed consortia to share existing physical resources like books, journals Ext...held by member library. The formation of any consortia is based on the fact that a group of library has a combine se of resource which is greater than the resources of any single number library (2).

The NISCHAR has cooperative acquisition erstwhile INSDOC, IN 1988 DELNET establishment and INFLIBNET 1991 beside establishment and number of libraries networks such as CALIBNET(Calcutta),BONET(Bambay),MALIBNET(Madras),MYLIBNET(Mysore),PUNENE T(Pune),HYLIBNET(Hyderabad),ADINET(Ahmedabad) and countrywide like ERNET(Education and Reserch Network) by Dept of Electronics, SIRNET(Scientific and Industrial Research Network) by CSIR this is exclusive for libraries

The need of consortia to provide common access to electronic resources across the internet in academic libraries. Consortia provided to library to save money, survive financial constraints and eliminated redundant resources and activities. The primary duty of consortium is to share physical resources like books and periodicals among member libraries. Consortium between publisher and librarian has gone under transformation of information technology which convert print media to digital media.” The emergence of internet particular to World Wide Web a new media of information delivery(has) triggered proliferation of web based full text online resources” (3).

The E-Resources cost were vary high. It is very difficult to subscribe E-Resources with in budget. Due to the cost effect it is challenge to Indian libraries to subscribe. There is another problem of increasing cost of publication and shrinking budget. Information explosion created confusion to find out quality information. An indualival cannot indentified a best existing a millions of content. To facilities quality information to library and information center required massive cooperation and collaboration. To satisfy the need of user and also benefit to libraries and technological provide network facilities and right information to right user. To clear policy frame work to ensure the acquisition of right content and resource sharing. In this context the Mobile Computing and Social Network sites for Ex:NewGenLib. The time come to one conclusion because of inflation and restriction and budgetary in library and research institute as whole.

International level large number of library come to gather with a joint hand to save the cost and better service to readers and sharing responsibility among the it members . Some f examples include London library Consortium and library west consortium. In present libraries reshaped themselves turn to digital world by varies mean and survival there is no place to stand alone library and information center.

The crisis its self witnessed from the last three years and USA and Europe and they commercialization of scholarly content due to the economic problem. Dollars spending library

may not be justification. Consortia themselves are changing vary rapidly as economic and technology demand new models for an effective survival.

Library consortia in India

The International coalition of library consortia has 200 library consortia from around the world (<http://icolc.net>). India occupied second place after China for subscriber of consortium based E- Resources. We have different types of consortia approaches like

- **Open Consortia**
- **Closed Group Consortia**
- **Centralized Consortia**
- **Publisher based Consortia**
- **National Consortia**
- **Budget Shared Consortia**

Below are some of the consortia examples Operating in india

- **NKRC(CSIR-DST)[Closed Consortium]**
- **INDEST(MHRD)[Centrally Funded Consortium]**
- **INFONET [National & Centrally Funded Consortium]**
- **DRDO E-Journals Consortium [Closed Group Consortium]**
- **CeRA (Consortium for E-resources in Agriculture)[Closed Group Consortium]**
- **DeLCON (DBT Electronics library Consortium)[Closed group Consortium]**

N-LIST (National library and Information Services Infrastructure for Scholarly Contents)[Centrally Funded Consortium]

Consortia	Established	Operation	Funding	Subject	No. Of Institution	Annual spending in Rs. Million (approx.)	Users (approx.)
NKRC	2002	NISCAIR	CSIR & DST,	Science Technology	65	600	10,000
INDEST	2003	IIT, Delhi	MHRD, GoI	Science, Technology and Management	1397	600	100,000
INFONET	2003	INFLIBNET, Ahmedabad	UGC	S&T, Humanities, Social Sciences	161	1200	600,000
DRDO	2007	DESIDOC,	DRDO, MOD,	S&T and others	50	200	7,000
CeRA	2007	IARI, New Delhi	ICAR, GoI	Agriculture	126	100	10,000
DeLCON	2009	NBRC, Gurgaon	DBT, GoI	Biomedical Sciences	33	80	2,000
N-LIST	2012	INFLIBNET, Ahmedabad	MHRD, GoI	All subjects	6000	-	-

Digital Preservation of E-Resources:-

Some of the project which started at international level for e-resources preserving

LOKSS:-

Digital content at various locations can keep safe for future use. It is a open Source software by Sandford University. Digital content of network based environment by keep multiple copies of a same book, software is free but membership to LOCKSS Alliance is essential for get access it general PC as LOCKSS Box is preserve digital content. LOCKSS Box performs the following Functions.

- It is a collective content from website through web crawlers
- It compare content with the same content collected by other LOCKSS Boxes
- It acts as web proxy and provides access to the publisher content.
- It provide web based administrate interface
- Monitor the journals which are being preserved and control access to preserved journals.

E-system of National Library of Netherlands :

National library of Netherlands (Koninklijke Bibliotheek) in Hague founded in 1798. It is depository library by the library act. It provide Online Public Catalogue in national bibliography. In case of open access publisher and non-profit organization no restrictions at all for KB staff both onsite and remote use allowed digital publication used as Intra Library Lone with in Netherlands sending the electronic file outside the library any other means is not allowed.

E-depot is term for KB Infrastructure of digital publication including Procedures, Workflow, Handling, and Achieving digital content. For this purpose software designed through IBM that is digital Information Archiving system software(DIAS). IBM has been granted intellectual property rights for DIAS.E-Depot has archived more than 5000 e-journals it has current capacity of 25TB. In future it extended upto 1.5 PB(http://www.kb.nl/dnp/edepot/operational/background/facts_and_figures-en.html).

PORTICO:-

It is a electronic service started by JSTOR in 2002 it focuses on preserving the intellectual content of electronic journals through file normalization and format migration(Fenton,2006)(9).

- Sign with Non-Exclusive archiving license
- Portico has right to ingest, archive normalize and migrate the content of publisher.
- Portico will serves as perpetual access mechanism and has to pay annual fee.
- Has supply source file in time

Library has to

- Sign an license agreement archiving
- Library should pay annual fee
- Library Should prove a details links of IP for user authentication.

www.aarhat.com
At this time there are 153 publishers on behalf of 2000 more association and societies. Portico has more then 13,919 e-journals and e-book of 129,890 besides 750 libraries. See <http://www.portico.org/digital-persevation/the> -archive-content-access/archive-facts-figures#page-1552.

The library gain campus wide access if non-availability of journal title from publisher website or any other sources. Even through portico will provide more service to library. In trigger event occurs like journal of audiology in Australia and new Zealand there available in all participated library through the portico website.

Conclusion:-

Concerted effort is being mode worldwide for consortia and digital preservation. But it is frankly said a journey of thousand miles start with a single step. In India library concrete take lead and initiate a long term preservation of content. To ensure that digital scholarship remains safe, accessible and useable for posterity. If no back file access, scholarship, cultural and social

heritage will be jeopardized it will against of 5th law of library science. India libraries to explore to create models for library preservation of e-resources subscribed by them besides options like LOCKSS, Portico, E-Depot, INDEST, INFLIBNET consortium should also permit to setting up of digital preservation project of e-journals

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